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ANNOTATION

This article provides information about a study conducted by the author that the physical fitness of children is one of the components of the complex sports training of chess players, which significantly affects the growth of results of young highly qualified athletes in the field of sports.

Key words: chess, chess players, walking, running, swimming, cycling, gymnastics.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ДЕТЕЙ, ЗАНИМАЮЩИХСЯ ШАХМАТАМИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлена информация о проведенном автором исследовании о том, что физическая подготовленность детей является одной из составляющих комплексной спортивной подготовки шахматистов, которая существенно влияет на рост результатов юных спортсменов высокой квалификации в области спорта.

Ключевые слова: шахматы, шахматисты, ходьба, бег, плавание, езда на велосипеде, гимнастика.

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SHAXMAT BILAN SHUG‘ULLANUVCHI BOLALARNING JISMONIY RIVOJLANISHI XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada muallif tomonidan bolalarning jismoniy tayyorgarligi shaxmatchilarning kompleks sport tayyorgarligining tarkibiy elementlaridan biri bo‘lib, u yuqori malakali yosh

sportchilarning sport sohasidagi natijalarining o'sishiga sezilarli ta'sir qilishi haqida olib borilgan tadqiqotlari bo'yicha ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlari: shaxmat, shaxmatistlar, yurish, yugurish, suzish, velosiped, gimnastika.

Dolzarbli. Dunyoda shaxmat eng mashhur sport turlaridan biridir. Shaxmat aqliy mehnat fonidagi emotsional yuklama bilan bog'liq kechadi. Shaxmat musobaqa faoliyatining bir turi bo'lib, unda sportchi jismoniy faollik bilan shug'ullanmasdan, balki raqibini mavhum-mantiqiy zabt etish uchun raqibi bilan musobaqalashadi. "Shaxmatchilarni tayyorlashda muhim vazifalardan biri kasbiy va intellektual tayyorgarlik hisoblanadi, chunki jismoniy tayyorgarlik sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirishda, shuningdek, umumiy chidamlilikni rivojlantirishda umumiy xususiyatga ega" [13]. Ammo, olib borilgan ko'plab tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, hozirgi vaqtda sportning jismoniy rivojlanishning yoshga bog'liq dinamikasiga va bolalar organizmining asosiy tizimlarini funksional holatiga ta'sirini baholash; jismoniy yuklamalar hajmining yosh, jins va salomatlik holatiga muvofiqligini aniqlash; yosh sportchilarning kasallanishi va ularning tibbiy faollik darajasini o'rganish; xavf omillarining ta'sirini kamaytirish, kasalliklarni erta aniqlash va oldini olish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlar ishlab chiqish; bolalarga tibbiy malakali mutaxassislar maslahatini tashkil qilish bo'yicha tadqiqotlarni o'tkazish dolzarb masalalaridan biridir [1,2,3].

Bolalar organizmi kattalarnikidan tez o'sishi va rivojlanishi, a'zo va tizimlar shakllanishining faol jarayoni bilan farq qiladi. Balog'at yoshidan sport bilan doimiy shug'ullanish organizmning funksional va moslashuv imkoniyatlarini ko'paytiradi, bu esa sog'liqni mustaxkamlashga, jismoniy va aqliy rivojlanishga yordam beradi [1,2,4].

Bolalarning jismoniy tayyorgarligi shaxmatchilarning kompleks sport tayyorgarligining tarkibiy elementlaridan biri bo'lib, u yuqori malakali yosh sportchilarning sport sohasidagi natijalarining o'sishiga sezilarli ta'sir qiladi. Bugungi kunda boshlang'ich sinf shaxmatchi-o'quvchilarining jismoniy tayyorgarlik tuzilmasi va mazmunini ochib beradigan tadqiqotlar deyarli mavjud emas [5].

Sport o'yinlarida mashg'ulot jarayonini samarali boshqarish ko'pgina omillarga bog'liq bo'lib, ulardan biri yuklamalar dinamikasi hisoblanadi. Sport nazariyasida uni o'rganishga ham mahalliy, ham xorijiy tadqiqotchilarning juda ko'plab ishlari bag'ishlangan [3,5,6]. Sportning turli sohalarida ushbu birlashma ularning o'ziga xos qonuniyatlariga muvofiq amalga oshiriladi. Shuning uchun shaxmatni sportning gipodinamik turi deyish mumkin, gipodinamiya esa nafaqat sport natijalarining yomonlashuviga, balki tayanch-harakat apparatining, qon aylanish, nafas, hazm qilish va butun organizm tizimlari funksiyasining buzilishiga olib kelishi mumkin [7,9].

Aqliy mehnat bilan shug'ullanuvchi insonlar uchun mushaklar faoliyatidagi kamharakatlilikni bartaraf etishning asosiy vositalaridan biri bu jismoniy mashqlar hisoblanadi. Jismoniy mashqlar organizmning yuqori ish faoliyati, nerv tizimining eng murakkab funksiyalarini davomli zo'riqish qobiliyatini yaratish va qo'llab-quvvatlash orqali insonning tabiiy zahiralarni ishga tushiradi. Bunda jismoniy mashqlardan umumiy ta'sir etuvchi (yurish, yugurish, suzish, velosiped, gimnastika va boshq.) va yo'naltirilgan ta'sirga ega mashqlar (nafas, statik, gimnastika) foydalaniladi. Mashqlarning aniq tanlovi va jadalligi sportchilarning shaxsiy xususiyatlariga bog'liq ravishda keng doirada o'zgarib turadi [7,8,10].

O'yinchilarning malakasi va musobaqalar qoidalariga qarab, shaxmat partiyasining davomiyligi 1,5 soatdan 6 soatgacha davom etadi, o'yin davomida 3 soatdan keyin muqarrar ravishda charchoq paydo bo'ladi va jismoniy hamda ruxiy bardoshlilik, shovqinga chidamlilik, shuningdek, shaxmatchining yurak-qon tomir tizimining holati kabi o'ziga xos bo'lmagan shaxmat omillari birinchi o'ringa chiqadi [11,12].

Ko'pchilik mualliflar shuni isbotlashganki, "... insonning aqliy va jismoniy rivojlanishi orasida yaqin bog'liqlik mavjud bo'lib, u inson organizmi va uning funksiyalarini o'rganishda to'liq namoyon bo'ladi. aqliy o'sish va rivojlanish mos keladigan jismoniy rivojlanishni talab qiladi. Jismoniy tarbiyaning sog'lomlashtirish vazifalarini amalga oshirish natijasida organizmning umumiy hayot faoliyati oshadi, bu aqliy faoliyatda katta mahsuldorlikka olib keladi" [10,13].

Shunday kilib, so‘nggi yillardagi mahalliy va xorijiy adabiyotlarda shaxmat bilan shug‘ullanuvchi bolalarning jismoniy va intellektual rivojlanishi, shuningdek, yosh bolalarda yurak-qon tomir tizimi va neyrovegetativ tizimining o‘zaro bog‘liqligi to‘g‘risida to‘liq ma’lumotlar mavjud emas. Bularning hammasi, shaxmat bilan shug‘ullanuvchi bolalarning salomatligi, jismoniy va intellektual rivojlanishining klinik-funksional ko‘rsatkichlarini baholashning dolzarbligini belgilaydi.

Tadqiqotning obyekti - sifatida shaxmat bilan shug‘ullanadigan 7 yoshdan 11 yoshgacha bo‘lgan 190 nafar bolani tekshirish ma’lumotlari, nazorat guruhi 60 nafar bolalar olingan.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Qo‘yilgan vazifalarni yechish uchun 7 yoshdan 11 yoshgacha bo‘lgan 250 nafar bola tekshirildi, ularning o‘rtacha yoshi $8,9 \pm 0,11$ yoshni tashkil qildi. Asosiy guruhni shaxmat bilan shug‘ullanuvchi 1 yildan 3 yilgacha tajribaga ega bo‘lgan 190 nafar shaxmatchi bolalar tashkil qildi, ularning o‘rtacha yoshi $8,89 \pm 0,11$ ni tashkil qildi. Tadqiqotlar 2016-2018 yillarda Respublika shahar shaxmat maktabi bazasida olib borildi. Nazorat guruhini shu yoshdagi 60 nafar Sirg‘ali tumanidagi 47-sonli o‘rta umumta’lim maktab o‘quvchilari tashkil qildi, ularning o‘rtacha yoshi $8,92 \pm 0,12$ yosh.

Yosh gradatsiyasining tahlili shuni ko‘rsatdiki, tekshirilgan shaxmatchi bolalarning aksariyati 7 va 11 yoshda (mos ravishda 29,5% va 23,2%) bo‘lgan (rasm.1.).

Rasm. 1. Bolalarning yoshga ko‘ra taqsimlanishi (%).

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko‘rsatdiki, shaxmatchi bolalar o‘rtasida o‘g‘il bolalar (78,4%) ustunlik qildi. O‘g‘il bolalar va qizlar o‘rtasidagi nisbat 3,6:1 ni tashkil etdi. Bolalarni jinsi bo‘yicha taqsimlanishi 2.-rasmda keltirilgan.

2.-rasm. Tekshirilgan bolalarni jinsi bo‘yicha taqsimlanishi

Birinchi bosqichda bolalarning o'sishi va rivojlanishi JSST standartlariga muvofiq vazn, bo'y va tana vazni indeksi (TVI) egri chiziqlari yordamida baholandi.

Bolalarning bo'yi vertikal bo'y o'lchagich yordamida, tana vazni – tibbiyot tarozilari yordamida o'lchandi, ovqatlanish holatini aniqlash uchun TVI baholandi. O'lchamlar JSST standartlariga asosan talqin qilindi.

Ishning ikkinchi bosqichida shaxmatchi bolalar va maktab o'quvchilarining somatik holati baholandi. Ko'rikga quyidagi mutaxassislik shifokorlari: pediater, otorinolaringolog, oftalmolog, ortoped va nevropatologlar jalb qilindi. Ushbu bosqichda barcha tekshirilgan bolalarda vegetativ yuklamani hisobga olgan holda yurak-qon tomir tizimining funksional holati baholandi.

Tadqiqotning uchinchi bosqichi bola organizmining jismoniy rivojlanishi, neyrovegetativ holati va yurak-qon tomir tizimidagi funksional buzilishlarni inobatga olgan holda berilgan intellektual yuklamalarga bola organizmini moslashuvini kuchaytirish bo'yicha taklif etilgan reabilitatsion tadbirlarni baholashdan iborat bo'ldi.

Olingan natijalarni amaliyotda qo'llash yosh sportchilar musobaqa faoliyatida o'z aksini topdi. O'z imkoniyatlarini munosib baholamaslik darajasining pasayishi va shaxmat harakatlarini bajarish jarayonida jiddiy qarorlar qabul qilish paytida qat'iyatsizlik orqali namoyon bo'luvchi ishonchsizlik kompleksining pasayishi, shaxmat taxtasida jiddiy voqealar rivojining davomini tanlashda javobgarlikdan qochish, sport natijalarini o'sishiga olib keldi.

12 oydan keyin kuzatuv guruhidan 18 nafar shaxmatchi shaxmat bo'yicha I darajali normativlarni bajarishdi; 10 nafar sportchi "Sport ustasi nomzodi" unvoniga sazovor bo'lishdi. Tajriba tugagandan keyin qisqa vaqt ichidagi musobaqa davri asosiy guruh shaxmatchilariga ma'lum darajada muvaffaqiyatlar olib keldi: 12 yoshgacha bo'lgan o'g'il bolalar o'rtasidagi O'zbekiston chempionatida 3 nafar sportchi g'olib va sovrindor bo'ldi; 2 nafar shaxmatchi shaxmat bo'yicha chempionatda o'z yosh toifasida g'olib bo'ldi. Bu yosh shaxmatchilarni jismoniy tayyorlash metodikasi ularning ruhiy jihatdan tayyorgarlik darajasiga ijobiy ta'sir qilishi va natijada, shaxmat mahoratini oshirishi haqidagi tadqiqot gipotezasini yana bir bor tasdiqlaydi.

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